

Riquelme, G.C., Herger, N. & Sassera, J. (2019). Theory and practice in secondary schools in Argentina: knowledge, experience or work practices? In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.125-136) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641884>

Theory and practice in secondary schools in Argentina: knowledge, experience or work practices?

Riquelme, Graciela Clotilde

Philosophy and Literature School of the University of Buenos Aires/Institute of Education Sciences Research, griquelme@conicet.gov.ar, griquelm@filo.uba.ar

Herger, Natalia

Philosophy and Literature School of the University of Buenos Aires/Institute of Education Sciences Research, nath@filo.uba.ar

Sassera, Jorgelina S.

Philosophy and Literature School of the University of Buenos Aires/Institute of Education Sciences Research, jsassera@filo.uba.ar

Abstract

This paper aims to interpret the meaning and orientation of practices for the transition to the world of work, as a compulsory curricular area of the secondary technical and vocational education in Argentina. The conceptual analysis is centred on the relationship between theoretical education and practice during the learning trajectory in the secondary and technical level and questions the meaning of practices, as a mean for the students to bring into play knowledge about socio-productive processes related to the work environment.

The results of researches of the PEET-IICE/UBA/CONICET allow for considering the objective conditions for the transition to the world of work in the context of provincial, economical and social inequalities and institutional differentiation in technical education. Finally, the article proposes the interpretation of the behaviour of some schools according to the modalities of training, level of consolidation, size, institutional profiles and the implementation of practices according to the social and economical conditions of their specific territories.

Keywords

technical secondary education; curriculum, theory and practice; comprehension of world of work; economic and social inequality; differentiation of schools and work and study practices; objective conditions of transitions to the world of work

1 Introduction

This paper aims to interpret the meaning and orientation of practices for the transition to the world of work, in a compulsory curricular area of the secondary technical and vocational education in Argentina. The conceptual analysis is centred on the relationship between theoretical education and practice during the learning trajectory at the secondary and technical level (Riquelme, 1993). The approach to the relationship between theory and practice as well as of the integration between curricular knowledge and experience become necessary to question the significance of practices as learning areas in which students must put into practice pre-professional knowledge about the social and productive processes of goods and services which may resemble future work environments.

The theoretical perspective of this paper responds to the researches and studies developed during the last decades by the Program of Education, Economy and Work¹ in the field of technical education and vocational training.

2 What do we understand by technical and vocational education?

Technical schools had an early beginning in Argentina with the establishment of the first schools of this sort towards the end of the 19th Century. According to Tedesco (1970) and Gallart (1983), the purpose of such schools was to provide education to students of low income and to deviate graduates from primary schools for providing the incipient industry with technicians. The curriculum followed the classification of the existing industrial processes in four areas: chemistry, mechanics, electricity and construction. The programmes included practical learning at workshops and theoretical studies of basic notions for operating these processes; there was a strong emphasis in mathematics, technology and technical drawing. Since the mid 20th Century, technical education consolidated, especially with the launch of the CONET (National Council of Technical Education) that grouped both secondary technical education and vocational training; furthermore, changes were introduced in the industrial technical education teaching plans.

A radical breakdown in the country's educational policy was marked by neoliberal trends of state modernization that set the transference of secondary education from national to provincial governments and the later restructuring of levels and cycles, during the first years of the 1990s, which withdrew technical education from secondary school.

A decade later and following different critical diagnosis about the breakage and fragmentation of the educational system caused by the nineties' reform, new transformations were attempted in the organization of levels, cycles and curricular plans in order to homogenize provincial differences. This can be interpreted by saying that during the last thirty years secondary and technical schools faced "critical transitions" (Riquelme, 2004) derived from partial or total changes of levels and cycles, changes of authorities and/or of the technical government of the level or modality and curricular changes of teaching plans¹.

Technical secondary education is currently organized in six or seven years divided in two cycles: the first one is to preserve the main core of common character to all orientations and modalities that may adopt secondary education; and the second cycle emphasizes in specific technical training and in practices related to each specialization.

Since the nineties' reforms, technical schools have changed their training profile traditionally intended for the incorporation to specific services (management, computing and tourism) and agriculture developed by each province. These processes have made technical education supply rather vague, and even similar to that of common secondary education.

3 Tensions between theory and practice at the curriculum of secondary and technical education: an old debate.

This section aims at defining questions widely debated in the fields of pedagogy, sociology and labour economics: the place of training and practice for learning and labour insertion.

¹Website <https://educacion-economia-trabajo-peet.org>

3.1 Theory and practice at secondary and technical school

The tension between theory and practice in secondary and technical education derives from the distinction between intellectual and manual work - thinking versus making - typical of Western culture. Thus, education is structured in differentiated modalities following such dichotomy and fragmentation, and hence stigmatizing the division between “education of the intellect” or “general education” and “practical education” or “technical education” (Riquelme, 1993, p. 3).

The first researches of María Antonia Gallart confirmed the existence of an educational rationality and a productive rationality; hence technical schools were shaped more similarly to other schools rather than to productive organizations. The specificity of technical schools is the presence of workshops that marked the separation between theory and practice; overcoming this breach constitutes a tension in technical education (Gallart, 1985).

Such division of fields of knowledge is deceptive; any subject or training proposal should contemplate both theory and practice, in order to ensure a proper approach to knowledge as well as an element of implementation to secure knowledge appropriation. The comprehension of a notion must include the theoretical positions and their implementation; therefore practices must build from knowledge.

Practices at the end of the training cycles prove the weakness of the contents of education (Riquelme, 1993): plans and programmes with encyclopaedist approaches, deep fragmentation between theory and practice, out of date contents and a certain inclination to their “telescopic/telescopización” through the mere reduction of the university-relevant subjects. Technical training itself is more theoretical than handcrafted; it supposes an accumulation of too many contents and no time for synthesis. This could be considered as “technical encyclopaedism”, because of the difficulties for making sense of what has been studied that entails. Technical education itself struggles between “knowledge accumulation” and the “ability for reasoning and practical implementation” as general education does. Despite a certain vindication of practice as a learning strategy over good theoretical teaching, excessive value is given to work practices, which usually translate into mere exercises of repetition or imitation of trades, allegedly fostering specialized training.

3.2 Curriculum and knowledge

Vocational training and education should exceed the teaching of contents merely aligned with work positions’ requirements, and voided of real knowledge and understanding of the world of work, its contradictions and technological changes. This has made it necessary to review the structure and the supply of cycles and modalities of the educational system – both formal and non formal-; the explicit contents, the type of scientific and technological education; the skills and attitudes developed and the level of projection of these towards social and productive reality (Riquelme, 1985).

The perspective of the French sociology of work focuses on the way knowledge from the vocational training may be meaningful for the industrial and sectorial activities, the “empirical- know- how” - the practical relationship that the worker maintains with the work environment and its objects -, and the “analytical- know-how” that requires conceptual-based intellectual training. Another distinction is the “partial- know-how” that is applied to a part of the work process and the “general and exhaustive- know-how” that allows for comprehension of work situations (Riquelme, 1991).

The notion of knowledge is the object of debate and study of many theoretical currents, and in the saying of Barbier and Galanató (2004) it is the objectification of knowledge in concepts and theories (cited in Herger, 2013). The question about knowledge is relevant for the development and comprehension of both curriculum and the differentiation between specialized knowledge and everyday knowledge or the knowledge through experience, without

leaving aside their relationship and the “pedagogization” of different knowledge for different groups of students (Young 2009). The boundaries of knowledge grow in significance for the creation of identities, hence for opening opportunities to acquire powerful knowledge or, on the contrary, setting learning barriers. Therefore, it is important to distinguish between learning at educational institutions, such as schools, and learning carried out at other places, such as home or the workplace. Criticizing constructivist or over-socialized perspectives, Michael Young and Johan Muller sustain that experience cannot be the basis for teaching plans, and that students cannot actually “build” their own learning (Young & Muller, 2013).

There are trends towards the modularisation of the curriculum, which put practice at the centre of teaching. Such trends have to be observed with precaution because they constrain access to the understanding and explanation of phenomenon (Young y Muller, 2016). The authors point out that these types of pedagogic strategies harm the disadvantaged students because they are excluded from the know that or propositional knowledge, and because of the acceleration of the progress of knowledge the elite groups can continue to ascend in the appropriation of more knowledge. These trends restrict the right to powerful knowledge because students cannot distinguish it or acquire it by themselves (Riquelme, 2016, mimeo).

From a didactic perspective, pedagogic devices become artificial in their providing simulations and decontextualization in favour of teaching and learning processes. Four types of vocational training may be distinguished: according to the instruments used, depending on the transmission of contents or the developing of abilities inside or out the school, regarding the asymmetry of the learning and teaching subjects and contemplating the relationship between theory and practice (Souto, 2013).

In the same way, some studies associate the notion of devices to the mechanism of mediation between the worlds of school and work, such as: training practices for students and teacher at enterprises, workers' training at schools, joint-programs with the community, research and development projects (Jacinto & Millenaar, 2007).

Some pedagogues assert that “if both types of education are indispensable for both the personal and the citizen development, academic education is equally necessary for vocational training” (Camilloni, 2006, p 5). It is known that the most flexible persons are those with a general education. There is “a so called new vocationalism that integrates technical, vocational and academic skills. There is a strong agreement that it should be provided technological-general and specific education as well general education with a broad base” (Camilloni, 2006, p.5).

3.3 Comprehension of the world of work and the culture for work

With the development of practices of study and work as a framework, the “comprehension or understanding of the world of work” should be highlighted as the idea of a profound revision about the current myths on education and work in different moments of the pedagogic work; the re-signification of the general and scientific-technological education; the use, recovery and update of disciplinary contents; a new meaning of the discipline as a tool for the better understanding of social and productive reality; an assessment of the practices of integration of study and work prevailing in middle education (Riquelme, 1993, p.12).

In this sense, and as a projection of the idea of comprehension of the world of work, institutions could outline problematic situations, laboratories, workshops, and a reflexive perspective at the social and productive reality though guidelines, guided observations and tours for students.

Recent developments aim at developing a cross-sectional axis to overcome isolated activities through the creation of a “culture for work” (Gómez Campo, 2006) cross-cutting school culture. This concept entails an interpretative and analytical comprehension of how education and work are related and the study of job opportunities or options after secondary

school. One dimension of this concept is the setting of pedagogic practices in which students are the protagonists, generating autonomy and the capacity for further learning and the approach of relevant questions of the world of work (problem solution skills, team work and communication).

4 Provincial economical and social inequalities and institutional differentiation of technical education: on the objective conditions for the transition to the world of work

The challenge of this paper was to introduce the perspective of the development of our researches on the relationship between education and vocational training, multiple social and productive demands and provincial differences among the particular responses from the schools according to their institutional profiles.

This way, the possibilities for considering or designing practices at the end of the cycle of technical and vocational schools would depend - to a greater extent - on the social characteristics of the population, the dynamic of the labour market and the demands from the local or provincial productive apparatuses, that are the socio-economic and political context of the schools and that settle the boundaries to the possibilities for the transitions to the world of work (at least on these territories).

4.1 Local and provincial inequalities

Argentina, likewise other countries in the region, has strong provincial inequalities resulting from a historic disparity in the productive performance that coincide with a high economic and social heterogeneity among and within provinces. This subject has been studied in previous decades noticing typologies of provinces according to their economical and social conditions (FUDAL, 1978; Riquelme 1978) and their impact in the living conditions of their population as well (FUDAL, 1978; Beccaria & Minujin, 1985; Anlló & Cetrángolo, 2007; Cetrángolo, Steinberg & Gatto, 2011)2.

The characteristics of productive apparatuses and of labour markets as well as the living conditions and even the cultural standards of the population in the localization areas of the schools influence the possibilities and decisions about the practices that students could do in their transition towards the world of work. The analysis of the provincial and local social and economic conditions for the insertion in the world of work allow to consider differential situations among areas according to the main productive sector, the labour markets' demands, the size of the populations and the relative living conditions, as well as the spaces or types of practices to be developed.

Thus, it is possible to distinguish among the contexts that present more advantaged social and economical conditions, with some advantages or limitations to those with critical or even strongly critical and isolated as presented below.

- **Advantaged social and economical conditions:** they correspond to diversified economic structures regarding activity sectors of great size, where employment demand is distributed between the modern industry and services; or areas with industrial or innovation enclaves that include large, medium and small enterprises with concentration of employment of high or medium educational level, even if affected by low demand; this can also occur in areas with dynamic agribusiness in current crisis. It usually coincides with large and medium sized cities and with small cities in dynamic socioeconomic contexts and with relative high social conditions. In these areas, there could be good conditions for the rotation of students of different modalities and specializations in the productive processes of enterprises of different sizes.

- Social and economical conditions with some advantages: areas with industrial and/or modern services profiles that include medium and small sized establishments employing workers with high and medium educational levels and where informal commercial and service activities co-exist. They are also characterized by withholding a developed public sector that employs professionals and technicians. In these areas, there could be conditions for the rotation of students of different modalities and specializations in the productive processes in different enterprises and in the municipal or provincial public sector.
- Limited social and economical conditions: they correspond to small or medium urban areas with an important weight of public employment as the main source of demands of workers, with lower economic development settled on personal and trade services. In these areas, there could be limited opportunities for practices, due to the low productive and commercial demands, leaving the public municipal sector as one alternative for the students.
- Critical social and economical conditions: they correspond to areas of low economic development with an agricultural or small business base and with predominance of the informal sector. There are unfavourable living conditions in rural or peri-urban areas in which the local public sector is a limited alternative of employment. In this context the practices usually occur inside the school and in some cases at the public municipal areas.
- Critical social and economical conditions of strong isolation and lack of demands: they coincide with isolated rural areas with serious social necessities and subsistence agriculture, where the local public sector is not an employment alternative. In these contexts, practices can only take place at school, although limited by the available resources.

It must be pointed out that in 2018, given the situation of Argentina at the time, even the areas with relative advantages suffered the consequences of the drop of the activity in many productive branches and the raise of unemployment and labour informality.

4.2 Differentiation of the technical secondary education

During the last decades, general secondary and technical secondary education went through reforms of the structure of levels and cycles and political and administrative changes that determined what we have characterized as critical transitions (Riquelme, 2004; Riquelme & Herger, 2015). During the nineties and since the Federal Education Act, the creation of the polimodal and the technical and vocational tracks brought fragmentation to the levels among provinces and the withdrawal of technical education. The Technical and Vocational Act (2005) and the National Education Act (2006) sought to recover and homogenise the level and its modalities, but starting from dissimilar situations of structure, curricular contents and coverage in the country.

No doubt, technical education was a level in check and the orientations of the national and provincial educational policies, as well as the not always planned reforms derived in 24 differentiated secondary education sub-systems with uneven duration and curricular design according to each province.

Technical education in Argentina was orientated towards the industry throughout the 20th century and towards technology and the new information technologies by the end of the century. During the reform of the 1990's provincial technical schools were merged into polimodals, and during the 2000's the so-called technical and vocational education rose combining the technical modality with both services and agricultural modalities. Currently, there are a diversity of specializations, the most representative of the industry are construction, electro-mechanics, electronics, food industry, chemistry and other processes industries.

The consolidation of the academic structure of cycles of technical and vocational education allows for differentiating schools and provinces, according to the moment of creation

and the implementation of the curriculum, or by the greater weight of the modalities industrial/technological, services or agricultural and their specializations. This way, different situations may be registered: completely consolidated technical schools, schools with consolidated modalities but in the process of incorporation of a new modality or specialization and even schools with different degrees of structuring of the cycles and schools or recently founded.

The size of the schools according to its enrolment shows a relationship with its characteristics because it gives a glance of their level of organization and student recruitment. The schools with a larger size tend to be located in urban areas and have more resources than those smaller institutions located at peri-urban or rural areas.

Institutional profiles reveal differentiation among educational establishments by their existing basic resources such as adequate building conditions, availability of material resources and the traits of their teachers (Riquelme, Herger y Sassera, 2018; Sassera, 2014). There are technical schools with adequate and sufficient buildings, material resources and trained teachers; technical schools with needs of improvement of their buildings, resources and teachers' availability, which do not interfere with their institutional functioning; and there are schools with greater difficulties that interfere in the institutional functioning and the implementation of practices.

The complexity of the differentiation of technical and vocational education in Argentina is expressed by the provincial differentiation explained above in addition to the differentiation derived from the degree of curricular consolidation and the institutional profiles. The following table synthesizes and illustrates the behaviour of some schools according to the industry, services and agricultural modalities considering the level of consolidation, size, the institutional profile and the carrying out of practices interpreted by the social and economical conditions at these territories. The cases have been selected from a study made by the authors.